

1 **mTOR deletion in the brain results in global loss of NAD energy transfer.**

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8 We demonstrate here control of energy by mTOR in the mammalian brain using a genetically engineered mouse model of mTOR loss. Deletion of mTOR in the mouse brain resulted in system-wide energy homeostasis loss manifested by silencing of the NADH dehydrogenases.

9 Citations

10 1. Lipton, J.O. and Sahin, M., 2014. The neurology of mTOR. *Neuron*, 84(2), pp.275-291.

11 2. Zhang, Z., Fan, Q., Luo, X., Lou, K., Weiss, W.A. and Shokat, K.M., 2022. Brain-restricted mTOR inhibition with binary pharmacology. *Nature*, 609(7928), pp.822-828.